

Design Verification and Failure Analysis: Tests on a Composite Bridge Structure

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ABSTRACT

The Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO by assignment of the Dutch Ministry of Transport, Public Works and Water Management (Ministry of Transport) designed a composite draw bridge, figure 1. The bridge is a Class 450 bridge (150kN of axle load) with a span of 10m and a width of 3m for an intensively used connection in Den Dungen, the Netherlands. In the development of the bridge the design needs to be verified by means of testing. Since no regulations exist for composite bridges, specific test cases were defined in cooperation with the Ministry of Transport.

Figure 1: draw bridge Den Dungen

Three test items are discussed:

- Impact and ILSS
- Bolted joint: large bolts in thick laminates
- Adhesive joint: the beam to top layer connection

Key terms: design, composite, bridge, test, analysis

1. Design rules

About 6 years ago when we started designing our first composite bridge we found that there were existing rules for the design of air and spacecraft, wind mill rotor blades and ship hulls, but that the design philosophy of these existing rules did not fit into the civil engineering practice, nor did they comply with the Eurocode design approach.

The Eurocomp Design Code and Handbook [1] provides a link with the Eurocodes and gives guidance for dealing with important issues like strength, buckling and joints. Taking this Handbook as a basis, in co-operation with the Dutch CUR Foundation and the Ministry of Transport we derived a simple and clear way of dealing with material properties, safety factors, and material conversion factors to account for fatigue and creep. The factors for all sorts of glass laminates are written down in the CUR-Design Rules for Fibre Reinforced Composites in Civil Structures [5]. Both the Eurocomp Design Code and the CUR-Design Rules have been used in the bridge design described in this paper.

1.1 General safety philosophy

Any composite structure or part of that structure must comply with the following condition:

$$S \cdot \gamma_f \leq R / (\gamma_c \cdot \gamma_m)$$

in which: S = solicitation (load)
R = resistance (strength, stiffness, stability)
 γ_f = load safety factor

γ_m = material safety factor

γ_c = material conversion factor

The load S and load safety factor γ_f are provided by the specific Eurocode that has to be met by the structure. The resistance R (strength, stiffness and stability), material safety factor and material conversion factor are dependent on the composite material, the way of production and the environmental conditions the structure is exposed to [5].

The design strength of the laminate is based on a general strain criterion. We use a laminate which has at least 15 % of the fibres in each direction (i.e. 0° , 45° , 90° and -45°). In this way one can always rely upon the fibres to do the work. Also, estimating the strength of the laminate gets quite easy: in every direction (in the plane of the laminate) one can take 1.2 % strain as a lower boundary design limit for tension, compression and shear (for tension one can allow an extra 20 % (=1.44 %), if needed).

2. Draw bridge design

Figure 1: draw bridge Den Dungen

By assignment of the Dutch Ministry of Transport we designed a composite draw bridge to span the Zuid-Willemsvaart at Den Dungen. In the design a steel upper lifting structure was combined with a full composite bridge structure. It is a Class 450 bridge according to the Dutch Bridge Design Code VOSB 1995; the design truck load for this bridge is 450 kN equally spread over 3 axles. The span of the bridge is about 10 m and the width is approximately 3.5 m. It is a movable bridge which means that there are many heavily and dynamically loaded joints. The exact dimensions and the locations joints are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Dimensions and joints of the draw bridge at Den Dungen.

The design process and concepts are further described in [7].

2.1. Bridge structure

In the bridge design the main structure was combined with the bridge deck to gain weight and costs, resulting in the design shown in a cross section at the rotation points in Figure 3 below. The integrated deck was feasible because of the small width of the bridge and the low stiffness requirement of $L/300$.

The bridge structure consists of 16 adhesively joined box beams wrapped in a cover laminate.

Figure 3. Cross section at the rotation points

The combination of bridge deck and main structure puts higher demands on the design of the top flange of the bridge. Due to the absence of a separate bridge deck there is no extra safety barrier against interlaminar shear fatigue due to the wheel loads, impact by falling objects and fire exposure.

2.2 Materials built up

The design is based on glass fibre stitched fabrics and resin infusion as manufacturing technique, with an assumed fibre volume fraction of 50%. Both polyester resin and epoxy resin were considered. For the box beam also pultrusion is an option, but because this project concerns only a single bridge, resin infusion is more appropriate.

In table 1, the safety factors (see 1.2) for this material and manufacturing constitution are given.

Table 1. The safety factors used for the bridge design

Factor	Value
Load Safety Factor:	static analysis: load factor 1.5 , dynamic load factor 1.2 fatigue analysis: load factor 1.0, dynamic factor 1.0.
Material Safety Factor :	1.6 (for vacuum infusion)
Material Conversion Factor:	Hot wet factor: 1.21 Fatigue (stiffness reduction): 1.1 Creep (using Holms and Just [6]): Quasi-isotropic $\gamma_{ck} = 2,31$ 55% oriented in 0-direction (in 0 -direction) $\gamma_{ck} = 1,46$ (in 90 -direction) $\gamma_{ck} = 3,31$ 70% oriented 0/90 laminate $\gamma_{ck} = 1,86$

Table 1 (continued). The safety factors used for the bridge design.

Factor	Value				
Fatigue effect on strength*: *Using S-N-curves, Goodman diagrams and Miner summation [2]	allowable amplitude stresses for E-glass-epoxy at constant amplitude load:				
	Number of cycles	$\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$	10^8	10^7	10^6
	$\sigma_{\text{amp}}/\sigma_{\text{TR}}$	0.1	0.133	0.160	0.192
	$\sigma_{\text{amp}}/\sigma_{\text{TR}}$	-1	0.158	0.200	0.251

2.3 Design verification

With the design guidelines described in 1.1 all elements, except accidents such as impact or fire, can be dimensioned. For the primary connections we found that the prediction methods for adhesive joints were not accurate enough as a proof of strength and tests are required. Adhesive joints are very sensitive for the assumed mechanical properties and for geometrical aspects that sometimes are not included in the stress prediction model. In addition to the analytical model of Volkersen we used finite element modelling for the complex adhesive joints, in a similar way as described in [8]. Tests are performed to verify the strength and FE-analysis.

In composite material the bolted joints require a high tolerance. This means that they are very costly and on request of the Ministry we reduced the number of bolts to a minimum. Also in this case, we did not want to rely on our assumptions without testing.

The impact damage resulting from an impact with a certain energy level is very dependent on the structure itself, because the structure creates the boundary conditions for the impacted locations. For verification of the impact resistance of the structure and the damage tolerance under the cyclic wheel load, impact tests were conducted in combination with ILS fatigue tests on representative specimen.

In the next part our design methods for the impact, adhesive joints and the bolted joints with large diameter our design methods are explained in short and compared to the test results.

3. Tests

3.1. Impact followed by interlaminar shear fatigue

From coupon tests on interlaminar shear fatigue behaviour performed at the Centre of Lightweight Structures, it was found that the same S-N-curves suited for in-plane fatigue design could safely be used for out-of-plane interlaminar shear fatigue. However, a combination of impact by a falling object followed by interlaminar shear fatigue due to the wheel loads could only be assessed by testing.

For the impact test, a 50 kg steel cylinder with a rounded head was dropped from a height of 1.3m on the 42 mm thick top flange. The first specimen were made out of glass fibre reinforced plastics. The impact causes a circular area of delaminations as can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Impact damage (E-glass-polyester) due to impact of 50 kg from 1.3 m without wearing course.

The presence of the wearing course of the road deck, consisting of a grit layer embedded in an epoxy adhesive proved to have a beneficial effect. This layer significantly reduced the impact damage as can be seen from the picture below (figure 5).

Figure 5. Impact damage (E-glass-polyester) due to impact of 50 kg from 1.3 m with wearing course.

Specimen were cut out from impacted plates and subjected to a cyclic three point bending test, to simulate the fatigue load due to the traffic, applying the same inter laminar shear stresses (figure 6).

Figure 6: three point bending test set up

The ILS-fatigue test however revealed a problem. The resulting impact damage of the glass-polyester specimen was quite large, and the damage growth under the cyclic load was unacceptable (figure 7). The damage progress was so fast, that an unimpacted specimen was also subjected to the test and unexpectedly this also failed within the 1 million cycles (figure 8).

Figure 7: example of failed specimen

Figure 8: unimpacted glass-polyester specimen

after fatigue test

The first crack (figure 8, delamination at arrow head) initiates at the secondary bonding layer which is present in the structure between the box beams and the coupling laminate. This secondary bonding of the assembly of the bridge structure was included in the production of the test specimen and now proved critical. Solutions were sought in the application of flexible PUR and modified epoxy layers between top layer and the structure, but they proved not effective.

It was concluded that polyester resins did not perform sufficiently well, mainly due to bad secondary bonding and shrinkage effects. Though secondary bonding effects can be reduced by proper surface preparation, we do not want any critical joint to be too sensitive for mistakes in manufacturing. Robust and fool proof solutions must be provided.

It was then decided to use epoxy resin instead of polyester resin. Epoxy has a higher inter laminar shear strength, is less critical on secondary bonding, and has a lower shrinkage resulting in lower internal stresses.

Figure 9: Impact damage E-glass-epoxy top flange

Figure 10: specimen after fatigue testing showing no visible damage.

Using epoxy resin in combination with a suitable wearing course finally solved the issue of impact and interlaminar shear fatigue. The impact damage is hardly visible anymore as can be seen in the figure 9. Also, in the subsequently performed fatigue test no damage occurred (figure 10).

3.2 Metal-composite bolted joints

The bridge has to be provided with several joints between the composite structure and metal parts. Adhesive metal-composite joints are considered not to be trustworthy because of the high eccentricity in the load transfer that occurs in this case. Fitted bolts are considered to be the only viable option. Nevertheless, in our design epoxy adhesive is still used to fill up the tolerances between the composite and the metal part. The design of the fitted bolted joints was done using the design rules of the Eurocomp Design Code and Handbook.

Figure 9 shows an example of the bolted joint at the rotation point.

Figure 9. bolted joint of the rotation point

The bolt diameter to laminate thickness and the edge diameters were maintained, but the Eurocomp Design Code prescribes that at least 2 bolts in a row need to be applied for each joint. This would mean at least 2 or even 4 bolts in each web or flange. To save labour costs, the number of bolts must be reduced. As can be seen, each side of the C-type fitting is connected with one single bolt. This is feasible, because it is assumed that no bending can occur and that all bolts and the steel C-fitting work together for each load in each direction. For such an important connection it is required to verify the strength by a test.

A specimen containing a single and double lap joint between a composite panel of 42 mm and a 20 mm stainless steel part was designed, manufactured and tested on fatigue and static strength.

Figure 10. Test set-up for single lap stainless steel-composite joint

The joint consisted of a fitted bush with a diameter of 60 mm (using a 20 mm diameter bolt inside and 80 mm diameter washers) and a 2 mm thick epoxy adhesive layer.

Design load

The design load of the joint was 225 kN (including load safety factor, material safety factor and material conversion factor) and could easily be met by the bolted joint. However, the adhesive joint already failed at 208 kN, proving that a simple adhesive metal-composite joint is not suitable.

Figure 11. Bolt hole of the single lap joint in the composite panel after ultimate load testing showing bearing damage at the top and first signs of tensile damage at the sides.

Fatigue test

The fatigue test consisting of 10^6 cycles with $F_{\max} = 90$ kN and $F_{\min} = 0$ kN gave an ambiguous result. The E-glass-epoxy composite showed no critical damage, but the 20 mm diameter bolt failed twice during the test, due to bending of the single lap joint. A thicker bolt of at least the laminate thickness should be used, preferably combined with the bush. The double lap joint of the specimen -which closer represents the C-type fitting of the joint of the rotation point- showed no damage.

Ultimate load

In the ultimate load test the joint failed showing plastic deformation at a load of 397 kN. The stainless steel plate showed plastic deformation and the hole in the composite panel showed delaminations due to bearing and was ovally deformed (figure 11). Also, the first signs of tensile failure are present.

Conclusion

The joint has a fairly high reserve factor for static loading. In the fatigue test the joint performed well, but the bolt diameter should be increased to at least the laminate thickness. Bending of the bolt must be prevented, either by application of at least 2 bolts as described in [5], or by application of a C-type fitting. A pure adhesive joint is not suitable.

3.3 Adhesive and laminated composite joints

Adhesive and laminated joints, although often used in composite structures, are hard to analyse theoretically. In the bridge structure many adhesive and laminated joints have to be made. For example between the box beams, but also between the wrapping laminate and the flanges of the box beam. The latter will be further discussed.

The static strength of the joint was determined using the analytical modelling of Volkersen as well as Tsai, which also includes the shear deformation of the laminates. Adhesive joints are very sensitive to the assumed adhesive properties, but also to the details such as the fillet of the edge of the adhesive (rounded or sharp). These aspects are not included in most stress prediction methods but we found that when performed correctly, finite element modelling of the adhesive gives an accurate indication of the effect these parameters (figure 14). One must be careful with singular points and apply an appropriate refined mesh [8]. The joint discussed here does not have a singular point.

Fatigue analysis has been performed based on the axle loads, the number of cycles, the wheel prints according to the Dutch Codes, a load factor of 1, and a dynamic factor of 1. For the epoxy adhesive, an S-N-curve has been assumed with a slope of 1 : 10 ($k = 10$) and an interlaminar shear strength of 15 MPa.

$$N_i := \left[\frac{\tau_R \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\tau_{gem_i}}{\tau_R} \right)}{\tau_{amp_i}} \right]^{10} \quad \text{and} \quad D := \sum_{i=1}^{19} \frac{n_i}{N_i}$$

$N_i = \text{life (cycles)}$
 $\tau_R = \text{allowable shear stress (15 MPa)}$
 $\tau_{gem} = \text{average shear stress } \tau_{max}/2$
 $\tau_{Ramp} = \text{amplitude of shear stress cycle}$

The predicted fatigue damage factor is $D = 0.019$, whereas the requirement is $D < 1$.

Because the joint is a primary load path, it must be tested to verify its strength. The test set up is presented in figure 12.

Figure 12. Load case and test set-up for box beam wrapping laminate joint

Although the wrapping laminate itself is sufficiently strong, at the crossing of the adhesive joint of the box beams part of the stresses will run through the adhesive causing the joint to fail.

The design running load of this joint was 1259 N/mm (including load safety factor, material safety factor and material conversion factor). In the test the joint failed at a running load of 1440 N/mm proving it sufficiently strong. Failure occurred in the adhesive; a crack runs along the corner of the box beam. See Figure 14 below.

Figure 13 shows the finite element model, which clearly indicates the stress distribution. It can be seen that the model predicts the stress locations, but more experience and reference testing is required to be able to rely on the stress predictions.

Fig. 13 shear stresses in the joint

Figure 14. Failed box beam wrapping laminate joint

4. Conclusions

The established Design Rules [5] proved well suited to perform a composite bridge design. Issues like impact combined with interlaminar shear fatigue, bolted joints of extreme dimensions, as well as important adhesive and laminated joints can be dimensioned with current design rules, but still need to be verified by testing. Test methods have been presented.

Testing sometimes reveals weaknesses due to effects sometimes not included in the stress analysis, but on the other hand sometimes shows large safety factors. The latter shows that improved prediction methods are desired, in order to achieve more efficient dimensioning, as well as to reduce the number of tests required for the design verification.

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